

Distribution and Taxonomic note on members of *Centranthera* R. Brown- A root hemiparasitic genus from Udalguri district, Assam

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Abstract

This paper discusses about the distribution and taxonomic details of two species of *Centranthera* R. Br., *C. indica* and *C. tranquebarica* from Udalguri district of Assam with updated documentation and descriptions. *C. tranquebarica* under the genus was recorded from the district as new addition to the flora of Assam in 2015 by the author. Taxonomic citation, detailed descriptions and distinguishing characters are illustrated with photographs of habit, flowers and key characters of the two species.

Keywords: *Centranthera*, Taxonomy, Distribution, Root-hemiparasite.

Introduction

The genus *Centranthera* R. Br. is an ecologically significant group of root hemiparasitic herbs or shrubs. [1], [2] The members of the genus are generally annual, erect or prostrate, 5 cm to 100 cm tall, root hemiparasite among angiospermic plants. Flowers are bisexual, zygomorphic, axillary and solitary. They depend on host plants via haustoria for water and nutrients. [1] Formerly placed in the family Scrophulariaceae, it is now placed in the family Orobanchaceae, under the tribe Buchnereae. [3], [4] The genus comprises six species worldwide with four species found in India. [5] The detail enumeration work of Assam flora recorded two species under the genus. [6], [7] Notably *C. indica*, *C. grandiflora* Benth. and *C. tranquebarica* are found in grasslands of Assam and India. [6], [8] This paper deals with distribution and taxonomic notes of *C. indica* and *C. tranquebarica* found in Udalguri district of Assam. In the present paper two species are compared, described and illustrated.

Material and Method

Udalguri district is situated in the central part of Assam that shares boundaries with Bhutan in the north part between 26°46'N – 26°77'N latitude and 92°08' E – 95°15' E longitude. The vegetation of the district includes semi-evergreen forests along the Indo-Bhutan border with patches of grasslands and deciduous forest.

Floristic survey focusing on the genus *Centranthera* under Orobanchaceae family were conducted in different reserve forests of the district-Barnadi Wildlife Sanctuary, Khalingduar Reserve Forest, Neoli proposed Reserve Forest, Bhairabkunda Reserve Forest and Rowta Reserve Forest during 2023-25. Morphological and distribution pattern especially of the genus *Centranthera* were noted along with their host plants. Two species under the genus were recorded; one of which was reported for the first time from Assam. [8] Plant specimens of the genus along with their associated plants were collected for herbarium specimen. [9] Confirmation of identity was facilitated using relevant taxonomic literature and consulting herbarium specimens deposited in Herbarium of BSI, Shillong (ASSAM) and Herbarium of Botany Department, Gauhati University. [6], [7], [8], [10]

Result

Taxonomic Enumeration

Centranthera R.Br., Prodr. Fl. Nov. Holland. 438. 1810.

Four species in India, of which two were recorded in the study area. [5]

Key to the species

Plants erect herb, growing up to 10-50 cm high

- a. Stems erect; corolla purple-red1. *C. indica*
- b. Stems prostrate; corolla yellow 2. *C. tranquebarica*

1. *Centranthera indica* (L.) Gamble, Fl. Madras 2:971. 1924; Pullaiah et al., Fl. East. Ghats 4:317. 2011. *Rhinanthus indica* L., Sp. Pl. 603. 1753. *Centranthera hispida* R.Br., Prodr. 438. 1810; Hook.f., Fl. Brit. India 4:301. 1884. *Centranthera procumbens* Benth., Prodr. 10:525. 1846; Hook.f., Fl. Brit. India 4:301.1884.

A hispid erect, subterete, branched herb. Leaves opposite, sessile, 2-3.6 x 0.4-1 cm, linear-lanceolate, entire. Flowers purple-red; calyx hispid, apex constricted; corolla 1-3 cm, upper lobes 3, lower lobes 2. Stamens 4, didynamous; filaments woolly. Capsules ovoid. Seeds striate, oblong-cuneate. Flowering: June-October. Fruiting: July-November.

Distribution: INDIA (Assam, Throughout India), BHUTAN, CHINA, SRI LANKA, MALAYSIA, THAILAND, MYANMAR.

Occurrence: Occasional along the river bed, in sandy soil.

2. *Centranthera tranquebarica* (Spreng.) Merr., in Merr. & Chun, Sunyatsenia 5:182. 1940; Pullaiah et al., Fl. East. Ghats 4:317. 2011. *Razumovia tranquebarica* Spreng., Mant. Prim. Fl. Hal. 45. 1807. *Torenia lepidota* Roth, Nov. Pl. Sp. 281. 1821. *Centranthera humifusa* Wall. ex Benth., Scroph. Ind. 50. 1835; Hook. f., Fl. Brit. India 4:301. 1884; Prain, Bengal Plants 2:578. 1903; Gamble, Fl. Pres. Madras 2:971. 1924. *Centranthera tonkinensis* Bonati, Notul. Syst. 1:337. 1911.

A slender, prostrate herb, basally hirsute, apically subglabrous. Stems branched from base; branches slender, mostly diffuse and ascending, dense, fascicled. Leaves opposite, rarely alternate below, sessile, linear lanceolate, 0.8-2.5 cm x 0.2-0.5 cm, entire and slightly revolute, apex acuminate. Flowers yellow; bracts longer than corolla; calyx ovate, corolla yellow, brown striate, 1-1.5 cm; lobes suborbicular; anterior stamens 0.3–0.5 cm; filaments densely white lanose villous; posterior stamens 0.2-0.4 cm. Capsule subglobose. Seeds reticulate, oblong-cuneate. Flowering: July-October. Fruiting: August-November.

Distribution: INDIA (Assam, West Bengal, Bihar, Odisha, Kerala), MALAYSIA, SRI LANKA, THAILAND, VIETNAM, CHINA.

Occurrence: Occasional in grasslands of study area.

Discussion

The genus *Centranthera* R. Brown, represents root hemiparasitic group of only four species in India and three species in Assam. [1], [5], [6], [7] Both species *Centranthera indica* and *Centranthera tranquebarica* occurred occasionally in grasslands and along the river beds of Barnadi river and Kalanadi river. Notable host plants of both species were *Cyperus compressus* L., *C. halpan* L., *C. iria* L., *C. rotundus* L., *Kyllinga brevifolia* Rottb., *Fimbristylis dichotoma* (L.) Vahl., that belongs to Cyperaceae family, *Imperata cylindrica* (L.) P. Beauv., *Heteropogon conturtus* (L.) Beauv., *Chrysopogon aciculatus* (Retz.) Trin., *Eleusine indica* (L.) Gaertn., *Eragrostis unilodies* (Retz.) Nees ex Steud., *E. atrovirens* (Desf.) Trin. ex Steud., *Sacciolepis indica* (L.) Nash., of Poaceae family and other members of dicots family Papilionaceae (*Desmodium triflorum* (L.) DC.); Polygonaceae (*Polygonum viscosum* Buch. -Ham. ex D. Don.) and Euphorbiaceae (*Phyllanthus fraternus* Webster). *Centranthera indica* was mostly observed among the members of Cyperaceae and Poaceae in the study area. On the other hand, *C. tranquebarica* was observed not only among monocot families but also among dicot family.

Fig. a: *Centranthera indica* (L.) Gamble; b: *Centranthera tranquebarica* (Spreng.) Merr

Conclusion

The occurrence of *Centranthera tranquebarica* from the study area is considered a significant finding. [8] The habitats of these species in the reserved forests viz., Kalingduar Reserve Forest and buffer zone of Barnadi Wildlife Sanctuary were under encroachment area for large-scale cultivation of cash crops such as tea and rubber. Despite the presence of such anthropogenic pressure, the study area continues to provide suitable habitat for the genus.

Declarations

Conflict of interest: The author declare that he has no conflict of interest.

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